

AWARENESS AMONG THE ELECTIVE OFFICIALS FROM SELECTED BARANGAYS ON THE DEVOLVED FUNCTIONS, SERVICES, AND FACILITIES IN THE PROVINCE OF BATANGAS: BASIS FOR CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on determining the level of awareness of the barangay officials and the level of implementation of the barangays on the devolved functions, services, and facilities as stipulated in the Republic Act (R.A.) No. 7160 and by the full devolution as referenced in Executive Order (E.O.) No. 138, series of 2021. In answering the research question, the study employed a research approach with a mix of methods that combined both quantitative and qualitative techniques. It involves the use of descriptive correlational research and thematic analysis. The study results show that the barangay officials were aware of the devolved functions, services, and facilities. At the same time, the barangays attained a high level of implementation of the devolved functions, services, and facilities. Moreover, the study also discovered no significant difference in the level of awareness of barangay officials on the devolved functions, services, and facilities when grouped according to the respondents' profiles. Furthermore, the study also found a strong link between the level of awareness of barangay officials and the level of implementation of devolved functions, services, and facilities. Based on the responses received from the participants, the study confirmed that barangays are currently facing several issues and challenges in fully implementing the devolution, including a lack of or insufficient financial resources, a lack of human resources or staffing, and inadequate support from higher LGUs such as provinces, cities or municipalities, and national government agencies (NGAs).

Keywords: *Full Devolution, Mandanas-Garcia Ruling, Local Government Code of 1991; Barangay Officials, Devolved functions, services, and facilities*

INTRODUCTION

Every state or nation has its ultimate goal, which is to enhance the overall well-being of its citizens. Within the Philippine context, the local government units (LGUs) are obliged to fulfill this mandate. Using these resources, the LGUs can efficiently and effectively carry out the devolved facilities and services mandated by existing laws. Because of decentralization, they can respond to their community's distinct issues and challenges. As a result, decentralization promoted greater responsiveness and accountability in every LGU.

Devolution has empowered the LGUs by granting them power and resources. It enables them to continually enhance public services provision, participatory governance at the local levels, and needed policies that promote socio-economic growth and development. Additionally, devolution is vital to addressing differences between rural and urban communities by promoting equity and inclusivity. Lastly, it provides equal access to essential services, infrastructure development, and economic opportunities by serving as a link to address the gaps in sustainability.

The Philippines' decentralization effort began with the Local Government Code (LGC) of 1991, also known as the Republic Act (R.A.) No. 7160. The statute empowered local governments to manage their resources to benefit their inhabitants. Each LGU shall provide the basic facilities and services concerning national policies, standards, and guidelines that already exist following the Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of LGC of 1991. As a result of decentralization, some functions, services, and facilities (FSFs) have been devolved to different levels of LGUs, like the barangays from the national government.

Internal Revenue Allotments (IRAs), a crucial element of financial decentralization, have been given to LGUs to ensure they can execute their mandated roles and responsibilities. According to Article X, Section 6 of the Philippine Constitution, LGUs are eligible for an equal share of national tax collections. However, as mandated by the Constitution, the Mandanas-Garcia Ruling raised the share of national taxes received by LGUs, significantly changing the decentralized picture. (G.R. Nos. 199802 and 208488, Mandanas et al. v. Executive Secretary, et al.)

Beginning Fiscal Year (F.Y.) 2022, the LGUs' IRA shares will increase based on the tax collected by the national government. It is brought about by the execution of the Mandanas-Garcia Ruling and per Section 284 of LGC of 1991, in which the LGUs' fair share from taxes collected by the national government is based on the third previous year of the present F.Y. Therefore, it is expected that starting in F.Y. 2022, the LGUs' overall shares of national taxes will rise considerably. This significant increase in the LGUs' portion of shares from national taxes will allow them to better serve their residents by providing basic services and facilities and assist them in carrying out other responsibilities assigned to them under Section 17 of R.A. No. 7160.

Executive Order (E.O.) No. 138 series of 2021, "Full Devolution of Certain Functions of the Executive Branch to Local Governments, Creation of Committee on

Devolution, and for Other Purposes," was signed into law on the first day of July 2021 by President Rodrigo R. Duterte. As mentioned above, the E.O. aims to aid in and direct the shift toward full devolution to successfully execute the Supreme Court's decision in the Madanas-Garcia Cases beginning in Fiscal Year 2022.

The barangay, regarded as the fundamental political or administrative unit, is crucial in advancing the well-being of all its inhabitants. Additionally, according to Section 384 of the LGC, the barangay coordinates and executes all government policies, plans, programs, activities, and projects within the community. Following the Mandanas-Garcia Ruling (G.R. Nos. 199802/ 208488), which brought about full devolution, the national government ensured that decentralization improves all citizens' welfare and keeps LGUs operating more efficiently. Furthermore, the national government must guarantee that the LGUs, especially the barangays, receive an equal share of the national government tax collections.

During the guidelines' implementation on full devolution in 2021, the researcher noted that the barangay officials raised several issues, including a lack of funding, staff, and technical capacity to carry out the devolved FSFs. As a result, the problems and challenges the LGUs face in implementing full devolution should be fully understood, particularly from the viewpoint of the barangay's grassroots level. In this way, the researcher can formulate a necessary intervention plan will be crafted to address the barangays' identified issues and challenges.

The study's results will help the national government agencies and higher LGUs to develop a priority capacity development intervention that will enhance and strengthen the capacities of the barangay officials and the barangays in implementing their devolved FSFs. In the long run, these capacity development interventions will improve the performance and service delivery of barangays geared towards enhancing every individual's life in the community.

Research Questions

This study assesses the significant relationship between the barangay officials' awareness level and the barangays' implementation level on the devolved functions, services, and facilities outlined in Section 17 of LGC of 1991. Moreover, the study also determined the issues and challenges concerning implementing full devolution to serve as the basis for identifying capacity development interventions.

Specifically, this study intended to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. educational attainment;
 - 1.4. Years of service as barangay officials?
2. What is the profile of the respondent's barangay in terms of:

- 2.1. classification;
- 2.2. Internal Revenue Allotment (IRA) shares;
- 2.3. type of LGU where the barangay is located;
- 2.4. income class?
3. What is the level of awareness of barangay officials on the devolved functions, services, and facilities in terms of:
 - 3.1. agricultural support services;
 - 3.2. health and social services;
 - 3.3. services and facilities related to general hygiene and sanitation, beautification, and solid waste collection;
 - 3.4. maintenance of Katarungang Pambarangay;
 - 3.5. maintenance of barangay roads and bridges;
 - 3.6. maintenance of the water supply system;
 - 3.7. infrastructure facilities;
 - 3.8. Information and Reading Center;
 - 3.9. satellite or public market?
4. What is the current level of implementation of the devolved functions, services, and facilities of the barangays in terms of:
 - 4.1. agricultural support services;
 - 4.2. health and social services;
 - 4.3. services and facilities related to general hygiene and sanitation, beautification, and solid waste collection;
 - 4.4. maintenance of Katarungang Pambarangay;
 - 4.5. maintenance of barangay roads and bridges;
 - 4.6. maintenance of the water supply system;
 - 4.7. infrastructure facilities;
 - 4.8. Information and Reading Center;
 - 4.9. satellite or public market?
5. Is there a significant difference in the barangay officials' level of awareness of the devolved functions, services, and facilities when grouped according to the respondents' profiles?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of awareness of the barangay officials and the level of implementation of barangays on the devolved functions, services, and facilities?
7. What issues and challenges do the barangays face in implementing the full devolution?
8. What capacity development interventions are needed by the barangays to implement the full devolution?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In responding to the research problems, this study employed a design combining methods incorporating qualitative and quantitative aspects. The researcher used quantitative method in this study to gather the respondents' profile, like years of service

as barangay officials, educational attainment, age and sex; barangays' profile of each respondent, such as classification, income class, type of LGU where the barangay is located, and average IRA shares; the barangay officials' awareness level on the devolved FSFs outlined in Section 17 of RA 7160 as well as the barangays' level of implementation of such devolved functions.

Additionally, this study employed a descriptive correlational study approach. The descriptive study methodology was successful and suitable in assessing the respondents' demographics, such as years of service as barangay officials, educational attainment, age, and sex, including the profile of their respective barangays in terms of classification, type of LGU where the barangay is located, income class, and average IRA shares. It was additionally utilized to investigate the level of understanding among barangay officials and the implementation of devolved services and facilities.

Further, the researcher employed a theme-based approach to arrange and evaluate the qualitative information. A codebook thematic analysis was used in this study to determine the issues and challenges that barangays confront while trying to implement full devolution.

Population and Sampling Technique

The study's participants were Punong Barangays from several cities and municipalities in Batangas Province. Furthermore, the study's population comprises 1,078 barangays.

The research sample was chosen using a method of probability sampling, specifically stratified random sampling processes. The stratified selection at random will be employed to split the population into similar strata or subgroups according to the cities or municipalities where the barangays are situated.

Respondents of the Study

The study's respondents were 292 Punong Barangays from 1,078 barangays in different cities and municipalities of Batangas Province. Based on the sampling techniques, the respondents will be divided equally per Congressional District.

Research Instrument

The primary data collection instruments in this study were a questionnaire for surveys and a guide to the interview questionnaire, both designed by the researcher. The development of these instruments was based on the research title and informed by existing related studies and literature. The researcher carefully constructed the questionnaires to guarantee that the information collected was relevant and valuable for addressing the study's aims, including pertinent questions and items related to the research problem.

In this study, the researcher crafted a questionnaire about the respondents' profile, the respondent's barangay profile, the barangay officials' awareness level, and the

barangays' implementation level on the devolved FSFs cited in Section 17 of R.A. No. 7160, which is divided into four (4) parts. The statements in the said instrument were formed based on various literates reviewed.

Part I provides the respondents' profiles, including age, sex, educational attainment, and years of service as barangay officials.

Part II contains the respondent's barangay profile, including the classification of barangays, average IRA shares from 2020-2023, the type of LGU where the barangay is located, and the income class classification.

Part III comprises the barangay officials' level of awareness, particularly of punong barangays, on the devolved FSFs cited in Section 17 of R.A. No. 7160, which were rated by the respondents using the four (4)-point Likert scale. The Likert scale assigns quantitative values to qualitative data so that the researcher can statistically analyze it. The rating system is as follows:

Numerical Rating	Scale	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.5 – 4.0	Very Aware
3	2.5 – 3.49	Aware
2	1.5 – 2.49	Somewhat Aware
1	1.0 – 1.49	Not Aware

Part IV involves the current level of implementation of the barangays on the devolved FSFs cited in Section 17 of LGC, which were rated by the respondents using the five (5)-point Likert rating scale. It is a means of assigning quantitative values to qualitative data so that the researcher can statistically analyze it. The rating system is as follows:

Numerical Rating	Scale	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.5 - 5.0	Advanced Level of Implementation
4	3.5 – 4.4	High level of Implementation
3	2.5 – 3.4	Medium level of Implementation
2	1.5 – 2.4	Low level of implementation
1	1.00 – 1.4	No implementation at all

Additionally, the researcher crafted an interview guide questionnaire to determine the issues and challenges the barangays face in implementing the devolution.

Data Gathering Procedure

As part of the data gathering, the researcher considered the following procedures:

1. The primary data collection tool, a survey instrument, was discussed with the research adviser for suggestions and input. Three validators with expertise in the field of study validated the instrument's content. In addition, the researcher utilized Cronbach's Alpha dependability to assess its dependability in pilot research with 25 participants.
2. The researcher made necessary revisions to the survey questionnaire based on the input, comments, and suggestions of the adviser, statistician, and validators. After finalizing the survey questionnaire, an online survey form was also created.
3. The researcher wrote a letter to the DILG Provincial Director and Local Chief Executives, requesting authorization to conduct the study, disseminate the survey online, and conduct face-to-face or virtual interviews.
4. For online distribution, the researcher coordinated with the respective C/MLGOO of every city and municipality to send the link to the online survey through an online platform to barangay officials within their area of responsibility. Data was also retrieved using that online platform. For virtual or face-to-face interviews, the researcher also coordinated with the C/MLGOO of the concerned Punong Barangays.
5. Data were collected and carefully organized for tabulation and analysis using Excel. The collected data underwent statistical treatment and analysis using the Predictive Analytic Software (PASW) version 26. On the other hand, data collected from the interview was analyzed by the statistician using thematic analysis.
6. The researcher upheld ethical standards throughout the data collection and prioritized the respondents' confidentiality agreement. The information collected was only utilized for this research study and other relevant academic endeavors, and the anonymity of the data is protected.
7. The researcher duly acknowledged the literature sources used for this study in the discussions and reference section with citations and references. This ensured that ideas were properly attributed, avoided plagiarism, and gave readers access to the referred works for additional research.
8. The data and findings were the basis for the proposed capacity-building interventions, which the researcher will submit to the appropriate agency for possible consideration and implementation.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After being collected from respondents, the researcher processed and evaluated the data using various statistical methods to present, analyze, and interpret the results. To address the research problem and assess the collected data, the researcher employed the subsequent statistical instruments:

1. Frequency count and percentage were used to answer Problem No. 1, the respondents' profile, and Problem No. 2, the respondents' barangay profile.
2. Standard Deviation Weighted Mean was applied to examine Problem No. 3, which concerned barangay officials' awareness of devolved services and facilities, and Problem No. 4, which examined the level of implementation of these devolved services and facilities among the barangays.

3. The researcher utilized the Kruskal Wallis H and Mann-Whitney U tests to identify a significant variance in barangays' awareness level of the devolved FSFs when classified by profile.
4. This study employed Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient (Spearman's rho) to determine the significant link between barangay officials' awareness and barangays' implementation of devolved FSFs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1.1: Profile of the Respondents as to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage %
18-24 years old	4	1.4
25-34 years old	21	7.2
35-44 years old	51	17.5
45-54 years old	99	33.9
55-64 years old	82	28.1
65 years old and above	35	12.0
Total	292	100

Table 1.1 affirms the respondents' age profile. The most significant proportion (33.9%) are between 45 and 54 years old, and 28.1% are between 55 and 64 years old, accounting for more than 60% of the sample. The youngest age group (18 – 24) is minimally represented at 1.4%.

This indicates that a significant portion of the surveyed Punong Barangays are between 45 and 54 and 55 and 64. The data also reflects a generation gap in local governance, with older individuals more likely to hold traditional leadership positions. According to Floranza (2021), this age group is often seen as combining youthful enthusiasm with extensive experience, which is crucial for effective barangay leadership. Moreover, middle-aged leaders frequently bring vitality and seasoned judgment to their responsibilities.

Table 1.2: Profile of the Respondents as to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	173	59.2
Female	119	40.8
Total	292	100

Table 1.2 depicts the respondents' sex profiles. Males represent more respondents (59.2%) than females (40.8%).

The findings show that men hold more leadership roles in barangays than women. However, women's participation in local governance has been increasing. As cited in the study spearheaded by the Asian Development Bank (2023), although men have traditionally dominated local governance, there is a growing trend towards gender inclusivity, with more women assuming local leadership roles. This change can be attributed to gender empowerment initiatives and the increasing recognition of the effectiveness of female leaders in community development.

Table 1.3: Profile of the Respondents as to Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage %
Elementary Undergraduate	1	0.3
Elementary Graduate	5	1.7
High School Undergraduate	7	2.4
High School Graduate	56	19.2
College Undergraduate	62	21.2
College Graduate	157	53.8
Post Baccalaureate Undergraduate	2	0.7
Post Baccalaureate Graduate	2	0.7
Graduate School	1	0.3
Total	292	100

Table 1.3 displays the educational attainment profile of the respondents. A large percentage (53.8%) had completed college, indicating a relatively high academic attainment. A significant portion has at least some college education (21.2% college undergraduate). Only some respondents have education levels below high school graduation.

The findings suggest that a sizable proportion of respondents are college graduates, indicating an upward trend in educational attainment among community leaders. Dumlao's (2021) study found a substantial association between educational attainment and Punong Barangay performance. Additionally, Nur's (2019) research reveals that the performance levels of female Punong Barangays are greatly influenced by their educational attainment, with those possessing higher educational qualifications demonstrating better performance.

Table 1.4: Profile of the Respondents as to Years of Service as Barangay Officials

Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage %
1-3 years	87	29.8
4-6 years	72	24.7
7-9 years	28	9.6
10 years and above	105	36.0
Total	292	100

Table 1.4 illustrates the respondents' profile regarding years of service as barangay officials. Most respondents have significant experience, with 36.0% having ten years or more in service. Those with less than four years of service constitute a substantial segment (29.8%). On the other hand, the least number of respondents had 7 – 9 years of experience, which was 9.6%.

This suggests that most respondents are serving their third term in office, reflecting a trend of long-term leadership among barangay officials. Such long terms in government have significant implications for the local government and the growth of communities. Leadership with over ten years of service tend to have a solid local governance background. Walker and Andrews (2020) claim that leaders with more years in office generally offer better governance outcomes because of their acquired knowledge and stronger community relationships. Similarly, Malemane and Nel-Sanders (2021) note that more extended periods in government positions frequently result in improved organizational expertise and knowledge, leading to enhanced governance. Seasoned officials can deal with bureaucratic procedures while carrying out regulations efficiently.

2. Profile of the Respondents' Barangay

Table 2.1 displays the respondent's classification-based barangay profile. The data shows that 61% of the barangays are rural, while 39% are urban.

The findings show that almost all barangays can be categorized as rural. The above breakdown suggests that most barangays are situated away from towns or urban centers, typically in areas with low population density. The population's size is a significant variable in determining the IRA or NATA share for barangays, as stated in Section 285 of R.A. No. 7160.

Table 2.1: Profile of the Respondent's Barangay as to Classification

Classification	Frequency	Percentage %
Urban	114	39.0
Rural	178	61.0
Total	292	100

Problems in devolved FSFs are experienced at the grassroots level, especially in rural barangays (Dabalos & Diamante, 2020). The Asian Development Bank's 2019 study indicates significant variations in access to services and economic opportunities between rural and urban locations. It emphasizes the significance of focused actions for rural development and balanced regional growth.

Table 2.2: Profile of the Respondent's Barangay as to Average Internal Revenue Allotment (IRA) Shares from 2020-2023 (in Pesos)

Average Internal Revenue Allotment (IRA) Shares	Frequency	Percentage %
1 – 999,999	16	5.5
1,000,000 – 4,999,999	200	68.5
5,000,000 – 9,999,999	47	16.1
10,000,000 – 14,999,999	18	6.2
15,000,000 and above	11	3.8
1 – 999,999	16	5.5
Total	292	100

Table 2.2 presents the respondent's barangay profile as to average Internal Revenue (IRA) Shares from 2020 – 2023. Most barangays' average IRA shares range from 1,000,000 – 4,999,999, with 68.5%, while the least barangays received 1 – 999,999 average IRA shares with 5.5%.

The findings indicate that most respondents' barangays receive IRA shares between 1,000,000 and 4,999,999 annually. The barangays utilize these funds to carry out the devolved FSFs cited in Section 17 R.A. No. 7160. However, the significant discrepancy in IRA shares reveals that many barangays need more funding, which may limit their capacity to deliver essential services and infrastructure improvements. According to Gulane and Viray (2023), unequal IRA distribution might lead to differences in access to facilities and services among residents of different barangays, thereby worsening inequality.

Table 2.3: Profile of the Respondent's Barangay as to Type of LGU where the Barangay is Located

Type of LGU where the Barangay is Located	Frequency	Percentage %
City	75	25.7
Municipality	217	74.3
Total	292	100

Table 2.3 exhibits the profile of the respondent's barangay and the type of LGU where the barangay is located. Most of the respondents' barangays are located in the municipality, with 74.3% in the city and 25.7% in the municipality.

The findings indicate that most respondents' barangays are located within municipalities. This can be attributed to the country's more significant number of municipalities than cities. Additionally, the type of LGU where the barangay is located is a determining factor in the distribution of IRA shares, as outlined in Section 285 of R.A. No. 7160.

In 2022, the study conducted by the Bureau of Local Government Finance (BLGF) underscored significant differences in governance and resource allocation between municipalities and cities. Municipalities face challenges such as lower funding and fewer infrastructures than cities, which impact their ability to deliver services and implement development projects effectively.

Table 2.4 shows the income class of the respondent's barangay. According to the data, most of the respondents' barangays are in the first-income class (61%), with the lowest being in the fifth-income class (6.2%).

Table 2.4: Profile of the Respondent's Barangay as to Income Class

Type of LGU where the Barangay is Located	Frequency	Percentage %
1 st Class	178	61.0
2 nd Class	28	9.6
3 rd Class	40	13.7
4 th Class	28	9.6
5 th Class	18	6.2
6 th Class	0	0
TOTAL	292	100

The data indicate that most respondents' barangays fall into the first income class. This breakdown highlights many significant characteristics of local governments' economic standing and financial capabilities. Higher-income class classifications generally imply a greater income-generating perspective, which can lead to improved access to resources, infrastructure, and government services within the barangays. This economic standing is frequently linked with better growth prospects and a higher quality of life for citizens. Based on Diokno-Sicat (2019), higher-income barangays gain from increased economic stability, allowing them to support local development projects more effectively. Lower-income barangays need more finances, impacting administration and the delivery of services.

3. Level of Awareness of Barangay Officials on the Devolved Functions, Services, and Facilities

Table 3: Level of Awareness of Barangay Officials of the Devolved Functions, Services, and Facilities

Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Agricultural support services	2.77	1.04	Aware
2. Health and social services	3.62	0.68	Very Aware
3. Services and facilities related to general hygiene and sanitation, beautification, and solid waste collection	3.51	0.73	Very Aware
4. Maintenance of Katarungang Pambarangay	3.55	0.69	Very Aware
5. Maintenance of barangay roads and bridges	3.36	0.83	Aware
6. Maintenance of the water supply system	3.21	0.89	Aware
7. Infrastructure facilities	3.43	0.79	Aware
8. Information and Reading Center	2.88	1.03	Aware
9. Satellite or public market	2.62	1.15	Aware
Composite Mean	3.21		Aware

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Very Aware; 2.50 – 3.49 = Aware; 1.50 – 2.49 = Somewhat Aware; 1.00 - 1.49 = Not Aware

Table 3 presents the awareness level among barangay officials regarding devolved functions, services, and facilities. The overall mean of 3.21 implies that most respondents are generally aware. It means that barangay officials are knowledgeable and can somewhat explain the devolved functions, services, and facilities. Among the items cited, health and social services had the highest mean score of 3.62 with an SD of 0.68 and was interpreted as very aware. This is the highest-ranked indicator, suggesting that barangay officials are knowledgeable and can explain the devolved services well. This high level of awareness is due to the crucial role of social and healthcare services in community welfare and public health.

It was preceded by the maintenance of Katarungang Pambarangay with a weighted mean of 3.55 and SD of 0.69 and services and facilities related to general hygiene and sanitation, beautification, and solid waste collection with a weighted mean of 3.51 and SD of 0.71. Both have verbal interpretations of being very aware.

Meanwhile, other items were assessed as aware only, such as infrastructure facilities (3.43), maintenance of barangay roads and bridges (3.36), maintenance of the water supply system (3.21), agricultural support services (2.99), satellite or public market (2.62) and agricultural support services (2.54). This is the lowest-ranked indicator, suggesting that specific aspects of agricultural support services must be more well-known and prioritized among barangay officials.

As affirmed by the study conducted by Francia (2022), most of the punong barangays are highly aware of the devolved FSF except for agricultural support services, information and reading centers, and satellite or public markets, which are only aware. On the other hand, the Gallanosa and De Castro (2023) study shows that respondents are partially aware of devolution and its functions.

4. Level of Implementation of the Devolved Functions, Services, and Facilities of Barangays

Table 4 displays the current implementation level of the barangays' devolved functions, services, and facilities. In general, the overall mean of 3.69 indicates that the barangays have a high level of implementation. This suggests that the barangays are implementing the devolved functions, services, and facilities using their budget with some assistance from NGAs and higher LGUs. Among the items cited, the indicator "health and social services" has the highest mean of 4.09 with an SD of 0.92 and is interpreted as a "high level of implementation." In contrast, "agricultural support services" and "satellite or public market" have the lowest mean of 3.16 with SD of 1.14 and 1.27, respectively, and are interpreted as "medium level of implementation."

On the other hand, the barangays have a high level of implementation on services and facilities related to general hygiene and sanitation, beautification, and solid waste collection (4.03); maintenance of Katarungang Pambarangay (4.03); maintenance of barangay roads and bridges (3.87); maintenance of the water supply system (3.75); and, infrastructure Facilities (3.87). For the information and reading center (3.39), the barangays have a medium level of implementation. They implemented the service using some of their budget but with assistance from NGAs and higher LGUs.

The study of Francia (2022) affirms that most of the devolved functions, services, and facilities were fully implemented by the barangays except for agricultural support services and information and reading centers, which are partially implemented, while satellite or public markets are yet to be implemented. On the other hand, the study by Flores (2019) shows that the barangays in Makati implemented social and health services, barangay justice systems, infrastructure facilities, and solid waste management. However, the barangays should have given more attention to agricultural support services and the satellite market because they were not feasible. Moreover, Orcena's (2019) study also shows that barangays are compliant in providing health and social services and solid waste management. However, the barangay needs an information reading center and agricultural support services to be implemented because the barangay is situated in the metropolis.

Table 4: Current Level of Implementation of the Devolved Functions, Services, and Facilities of Barangays

Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Agricultural support services	3.16	1.14	Medium level of implementation

2. Health and social services	4.09	0.92	High Level of Implementation
3. Services and facilities related to general hygiene and sanitation, beautification, and solid waste collection	4.03	0.87	High Level of Implementation
4. Maintenance of Katarungang Pambarangay	4.03	0.93	High Level of Implementation
5. Maintenance of barangay roads and bridges	3.87	0.97	High Level of Implementation
6. Maintenance of the water supply system	3.75	1.07	High Level of Implementation
7. Infrastructure facilities	3.87	1.03	High Level of Implementation
8. Information and Reading Center	3.39	1.22	Medium level of implementation
9. Satellite or public market	3.16	1.27	Medium level of implementation
Composite Mean	3.69		High Level of Implementation

Legend: 4.50 -5.00 = Advance level of Implementation; 3.50 – 4.49 = High level of Implementation; 2.50 – 3.49 = Medium level of Implementation; 1.50 – 2.49 = Low level of implementation; 1.00 - 1.49 = No implementation at all

5. Significant Difference in the Level of Awareness of the Barangay Officials on the Devolved Functions, Services, and Facilities when Grouped According to the Respondent's Profile

Table 5 shows the barangay officials' awareness of devolved functions, services, and facilities according to their profile. The findings reveal no significant differences between groups, as the p-values were higher than the alpha level. This indicates that the responses are statistically similar, reflecting a uniform awareness across profiles.

Table 5: Difference of Responses on Level of Awareness of Barangays Officials on Devolved Functions, Services, and Facilities When Grouped According to Respondents' Profile

Profile Variables	χ^2_c / U	p-value	Interpretation
Age	8.156	0.148	Not Significant
Sex	9370	0.191	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	7.696	0.360	Not Significant
Years in Service as Barangay Officials	3.732	0.292	Not Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.05

Based on the previously mentioned study results, it is clear that barangay officials' awareness of devolved functions, services, and facilities is not influenced by their sex, age, educational attainment, or years of service.

A University of the Philippines backed the argument - Diliman study, which discovered that officials' knowledge about devolved services, such as health, agriculture, and social services, is consistent across demographics and professional backgrounds, suggesting no significant disparity in awareness levels (UPSaHalalan, 2019). Contrary to this, Floranza's (2021) research discovered that barangay officials' socio-demographic characteristics, such as years of service, educational attainment, age, and sex, affect their governance and awareness of devolved functions, services, and facilities. Those with higher education degrees and greater years of service exhibited more awareness and expertise in governance. Younger officials, or those who had yet to go to school, showed less awareness.

6. Relationship between the Level of Awareness of the Barangay Officials and the Level of Implementation of the Barangays on the Devolved Functions, Services, and Facilities

Table 6 indicates the relationship between barangay officials' awareness of devolved functions, services, and facilities and their level of implementation. The calculated rho-value of 0.532 suggests a moderate direct correlation, and the consequent p-value of 0.000 is below the alpha significance threshold of 0.01. This indicates a significant connection, indicating that higher awareness is related to a higher level of implementation of devolved functions, services, and infrastructure.

Table 6: Relationship Between Level of Awareness of Barangays Officials on Devolved Functions, Services and Facilities and Level of Implementation of devolved functions, services and facilities

	rho-value	p-value	Interpretation
Level of Awareness vs. Level of Implementation	0.532**	0.000	Highly Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.01

A 2022 study by the PIDS revealed that, while financial capacity and planning are essential, understanding among local government units (LGUs) about their devolved responsibilities significantly affects the delivery of services efficiency. The study points out the need for effective management of human resources along with capacity building to ensure that barangay officials are adequately prepared to execute devolved tasks effectively. Furthermore, the HKPH Public Opinion and Research Center's study, which was carried out in collaboration with the Asia Research Center, highlighted the crucial role of barangay officials in local governance. As stated in the study, increased awareness

and knowledge among barangay officials results in better service and function implementation (Manila Standard, 2023).

7. Issues and Challenges that the Barangays are Facing in the Implementation of the Full Devolution

The researcher interviewed nine (9) punong barangays in various cities and municipalities in Batangas. The participants are either in their second or third term as Punong barangays and have experience implementing full devolution. Participants' viewpoints are based on their knowledge of fully implementing devolution. The issues and challenges that the punong barangays face are divided into three (3) themes: lack or insufficient financial resources, lack of human resources/staffing, and lack of support from higher LGUs and NGAs.

Theme 1: Lack or insufficient financial resources

The IRA, now known as NTA, is a share that barangays automatically receive from national tax collections, as outlined in Section 17 of LGC of 1991. This funding supports the implementation of devolved FSFs. However, the IRA amount received by barangays often needs to align with the scale of programs and projects they must implement, leading to a need for more resources for effective full devolution.

Theme 2: Lack of human resources/staffing

Implementing devolved functions, services, and facilities requires adequate human resources and technical skills. However, insufficient financial resources often prevent barangays from hiring the additional personnel needed. With a sufficient budget, barangays can recruit the necessary staff to carry out programs and projects at the local level effectively. As a result, barangays encounter significant challenges and issues due to a need for more human resources to implement devolution fully.

Theme 3: Lack or inadequate support from higher LGUs and NGAs

Section 17 of the LGC of 1991 cites the specific devolved FSFs assigned to various levels of LGUs. It outlines each LGU's responsibilities and limitations in executing these devolved services. Higher LGUs and NGAs should coordinate their programs and projects with those of the barangays to ensure integrated development efforts. However, barangays frequently need more support from higher-level LGUs and NGAs while adopting full devolution, notably regarding financial or technical assistance.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions were reached:

1. Most of the respondents are 45-55 years old, male, college graduates, and have more than ten years of service as barangay officials.

2. Respondent's barangays are mainly classified as rural and located in municipalities with first income class and average IRA shares of PhP1,000,000 – 4,999,999.
3. Barangay officials are very aware of the maintenance of Katarungang Pambarangay and services and facilities related to general hygiene and sanitation, beautification, solid waste collection, health, and social services, and other devolved functions, services and facilities.
4. Currently, barangays have a high level of implementation for most devolved functions, services, and facilities, except for the satellite or public markets, information and reading centers, and agricultural support services, which have a medium level of implementation.
5. The barangay officials' awareness of the devolved functions, services, and facilities is similar when grouped according to the respondent's profile.
6. There is a significant relationship between the level of awareness of the barangay officials and the level of implementation of barangays on the devolved functions, services, and facilities.
7. The barangays are currently facing issues and challenges in implementing full devolution, which include a lack of or insufficient financial resources, a lack of human resources/staffing, and a lack of or inadequate support from higher LGUs and NGAs.
8. The barangays need the following capacity development interventions that will enhance their competencies as barangay officials and capabilities of their respective barangays in carrying out the devolved services in facilities which include the following: strengthening the barangays' innovative revenue-raising capacities to generate local sources of revenue through fees and clearances; ensuring efficient and effective use of financial resources; prioritizing projects and programs for implementation; seeking financial and technical assistance from higher LGUs and national NGAs; and establishing partnerships with civil society organizations (CSOs) within the barangays for program and project implementation.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions acquired from the information provided, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Conduct re-orientation or training programs for barangay officials to enhance their skills and knowledge of the devolved functions, services, and facilities. Focus on areas with lower awareness levels, such as satellite or public markets, agricultural support services, and information and reading centers.
2. Create strategies to improve resource allocation and management, both financial and human, to ensure efficient utilization of available resources. This can include planning, budgeting, financial management, and human resource development training.
3. Strengthen partnership, coordination, and collaboration with higher LGUs and NGAS in implementing programs and projects to ensure all efforts are aligned and

complemented. This involves regular coordination meetings, joint projects, and technical assistance provisions to address the issues and challenges of financial and human resources shortages. This will also help the barangays to implement devolved functions, services, and facilities with low implementation levels.

4. Encourage barangays to explore innovative revenue-raising activities as part of their taxing power, as cited in the provision on LGC of 1991, which can help increase their income. Activities related to revenue-raising include using barangay assets to generate income, updating their revenue code, improving fee collection systems, and establishing local economic enterprises.
5. Ensure the barangays focus on improving facilities and services currently underperforming, such as agricultural support services and public markets, by investing in constructing and maintaining essential infrastructure. Additionally, barangays can forge a private-public partnership to implement such infrastructure projects.
6. Create a local project monitoring committee to implement monitoring and evaluation activities regarding the devolved FSF implementation in the barangays. The committee will assist in identifying gaps, evaluating progress, and making adjustments needed to improve the implementation of full devolution.
7. As part of participatory governance, the CSOs can participate in the barangays' decision-making and planning process. This can be accomplished through regular community meetings, feedback channels, and joint planning sessions.
8. Organize information and education campaigns on the devolved functions, services, and facilities to ensure that barangay officials and their constituents understand its importance. This is meant to encourage the community's support and participation in various projects in the barangays.
9. Develop a capacity development plan to improve the competencies and capabilities of barangay officials in fully implementing devolution.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To ensure no harm occurred in this study, the researcher confirmed that all respondents voluntarily agreed to participate. Permission was obtained through informed consent, using the university's official letterhead outlining the study's purpose and data collection methods.

The researcher guaranteed that respondents' names and information were used solely for research purposes and maintained complete confidentiality. Additionally, the researcher prioritized the respondents' safety, and they could withdraw at any time.

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